

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESERVICE TEACHERS' PHILOSOPHY OF TEACHING THROUGH A SCHOOL-BASED IMMERSION PATHWAY

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Abstract - The development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching during school-based immersion was explored through an interpretivist case study and conducted via a doctoral study which involved an exploration of the development of preservice teachers' professional practice and identity. The experiences of six preservice teachers who participated in the immersion pathway in Australia were tracked by the researcher over a year-long period. Findings suggested that each of the preservice teachers appeared to perceive themselves as a teacher, no longer a university student, and they had developed a strong sense of alignment with the teaching profession. Additionally, the researcher found that the preservice teachers were able to explain their developing philosophy of teaching and connect their beliefs to their future as teaching professionals.

Keywords - Immersion pathway, Philosophy of Teaching, Preservice teachers, Professional identity

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the evolution of a philosophy of teaching that a small number of individual preservice teachers experienced through their participation in a year-long professional experience in a school-based immersion pathway. The exploration of the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching was derived from a doctoral study of preservice teachers' development of professional identity and practice. An important theme that arose from the experiences shared by the preservice teachers during their engagement in an immersion pathway was a Philosophy of Teaching. Preservice teachers' development of a philosophy of teaching in the current study was referred to by the participants in relation to the current and future teaching. The preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching appeared to be strongly connected to their perception of self-as-teachers, and their developing teacher identity was influenced in the year-long immersion pathway through a process of socialisation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Development of a Self-image as a Teacher

The development of one's identity is influenced by self-perception which is shaped and reshaped by experience (Beauchamp&Thomas,2009; Poulou, 2007; Wenger,1998).Danielwicz(2001) suggested that preservice teachers need to engage in a process of self-reflection about their growing professional identities based on their observations and experiences to provide alens through which they can develop an understanding of who they are with in the multiple role sand how others see them. Reflection on one's teacher identity appears to be a common activity for preservice teachers worldwide, and is often demonstrated through their articulation of their teacher identity through a written declaration of their teaching

philosophy (Caires, Ameida, &Vieira, 2012; Cattley, 2007; Haymore Standholtz, 2011).

2.2 Philosophy of Teaching

For preservice teachers, their production of either a written or oral account of a philosophy of teaching can form part of their interview process or application for entry into the teaching profession. In the state of Queensland, Australia, the process of teacher registration includes a requirement that preservice teachers submit their philosophy of teaching as part of their employment application (Queensland College of Teachers, n.d.). The researcher of the current study searched the literature to find a working definition for a 'teaching philosophy', yet there was little information available to cater to this inquiry. A definition produced by Moseti Ongaki (2014) identified that the development of teaching philosophy can be variously described or interchanged with terms such as teachers' beliefs, values, or teachers' reflections on their knowledge of teaching. However, such a lack of clarity of what a teaching philosophy is does not afford preservice teachers with an effective degree of guidance for them to construct a written and/or an oral communication of how their pedagogical philosophies are related to epistemological beliefs or preservice teachers' perceived future effectiveness as teachers (Moseti Ongaki, 2014; Sung, 2007). Several studies have described the development of an individual's teaching philosophy as something that evolves dynamically over time through one's participation in educational environments. McDermott (2008) argued that development of a teaching philosophy shifts over time and in relation to preservice teachers' engagement in different contexts and the different relationships made along the way that contribute to shaping their beliefs. Yet, preservice teachers' ability to align their knowledge of teaching with their philosophy of teaching during

teaching practice emerges as a potentially enabling or constraining influence on the development of an individual's teaching philosophy. Castellanos Jaimes (2012) suggested that preservice teachers are faced with challenges in connecting theory to their own beliefs and understanding. For example, when preservice teachers were taught about student-centred learning, they could describe the benefits of this learning approach orally in tutorials and in their written essays. However, when they were in schools many of the preservice teachers' teaching approach did not align with their idealised vision of teaching but was instead a teacher-centred approach they had described they did not want to do. In such cases as this, preservice teachers demonstrate a kind of 'lip-service' about their teaching philosophy rather than deeply considering what their real philosophy is.

Preservice teachers require guidance on how to critique teaching and learning theory on more than a superficial level and connect their learning to their teaching practices (Arrastia, Rawls, Brinkerhoff, & Roehrig, 2014; Castellanos Jaimes, 2012). Simmons et al. (1999) described this process as 'making explicit our implicit beliefs as well as our assumptions and values of our worldview' (p. 932). When preservice teachers are guided on how to reflect on their teaching philosophy they are able to gain a better insight about their beliefs and identify inconsistencies in those beliefs. Simmons et al. suggested that preservice teachers develop their pedagogical philosophies through the perceptions that they have of their social experiences.

There are several studies which have found that school-based professional experiences can influence preservice teachers' developing philosophy of teaching. Caires et

al.(2012)conductedaquantitativestudyof295preservice teachers in Portugal who were enrolled in a graduate program. One month before the end of their teaching practice, when the participants were asked to describe their perceptions of their teaching practice experience, they referred to their growing levels of autonomy, self-confidence, and trust about the quality of the skills and knowledge that they had acquired during teaching practice. In a US-based study, Haymore Standholtz (2011) researched the teachingpracticesof290 preservice teachers enrolled in undergraduate and graduate programs. During their participation in professional experience, the preservice teachers were required to write their reflections-on-practice to develop a sense of awareness of their teaching practice. This study found that the factor the preservice teachers most commonly linked to effective instruction was student participation. The preservice teachers recounted various strategies for involving students, highlighting the use of visual representation, games, and hands-on activities. Preservice teachers in this study frequently expressed the need to align their teaching with their professional teaching standards and to cover

established curriculum during a set timeframe. Preservice teachers in the current research were not required to take on a teaching role in the immersion pathway. Yet, they were required to align their teaching with the Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (n.d.) during their professional experience in preparation for writing their philosophy of teaching statements.

Preservice teachers' development of a philosophy of teaching can be influenced by engagement in self-reflection. Preservice teachers' writing of philosophy statements can be understood as tools to critique their lesson planning and teaching practices with their teaching beliefs (Gilbert, 2009).InCattley's (2007)small scale Australia-based qualitative study, preservice teachers were required to engage in reflective writing exercises by giving consideration to their responses to, and observations of, various elements of the teaching environment such as daily class room interruptions, parentliaison episodes, and staff room activities. Cattley found that completing reflections provided preservice teachers with a more thorough understanding of the breadth and complexity of the teacher's role in professional teacher identity formation. In the current study, participation in the year-long immersion pathway contributed in part to how they saw their teaching philosophy develop over the course of the year and the experiences that they shared about their teaching practices, their successes and failures, and their self-reflection on professional practice was integral to developing an understanding of their evolution as emerging teachers.

III. METHODOLOGY

In the current study, an interpretivist, qualitative approach was used for a case study-based exploration of the preservice teachers' lived experiences resulting from social interactions whereby they interpreted and made meaning of their own and others' actions through jointly constructed understandings (Merriam, 1998). Case study was used to develop a rich picture that allowed for analytical insights of the preservice teachers' professional identity development, in its completeness and in looking at it from a variety of angles (Stake, 2005; Thomas, 2014). Interactions via a moderated online discussion board throughout the year-long immersion pathway gave participants various opportunities to share their experiences. Thematic analysis was used in the research to identify, analyse, and report patterns of themes within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006).The researcher made notes of themes not explicitly sought out in the data and used a quasi-constant comparative method of analysis to analyse data from different people over different times (Glaser & Straus, 1967). Furthermore, an adapted form of Boeije's (2002) approach to using constant comparative method analysis was implemented in order to: compare/contrast within an

individual and group interview; compare/contrast between the three rounds of interviews; compare/contrast between online discussion board postings; and compare/contrast artefacts with interview and discussion board data. The researcher sought to compare and contrast the commonalities and differences in preservice teachers' perceptions of their experiences as the data were gathered, which occurred both at the time of collection and retrospectively to compare/contrast new data with that already gathered. Data were collected throughout the year-long immersion pathway experience as described in Table 1.1.

IV. PARTICIPANTS

Six 4th year preservice teachers, studying in their final year of a Bachelor of Education program at an Australian university, volunteered to participate in this study. The participants were aged from 21 to 45 years old and located at various school sites (see Table 1.2). The participants were engaged in a year-long, school-based immersion pathway that started prior to the first day of the school year and continued to the end of the school year. The immersion pathway included 20+ days of voluntary immersion and 60 days of placements in the 2015 school year. Pseudonyms were used for the protection of the participants' privacy. The researcher had no influence over any assessment or grading of the participants' coursework or professional experience.

V. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The overarching research question was:
What experiences do preservice teachers perceive as providing insights into the profession and in developing an identity of belonging in the profession? There were two sub-questions to explore preservice teachers' identity development:

1. How do preservice teachers develop an identity as a teacher through their immersion in a professional community?
2. How do preservice teachers develop professional practice through their immersion in a professional community?

The experiences shared by participants of their development of professional practice and identity during their engagement in a school-based immersion pathway resulted in one of several themes which evolved in data analysis, that is, a Philosophy of Teaching.

VI. FINDINGS

The preservice teachers from the current study appeared to be very aware of how they would write their philosophy statement for teacher registration. In

describing their professional identity beliefs about teaching and learning the data revealed that the theme of Philosophy of Teaching consisted of two categories: a) current teaching, and b) future teaching.

6.1 Current Teaching

Participation in the immersion pathway placed each of the preservice teachers in a position to reflect on their professional practice and identity. Through their engagement in the immersion pathway, each of the preservice teachers appeared to perceive themselves as a teacher, and no longer as a university student. They also seemed to have developed a strong sense of alignment with the teaching profession. Evidently, each of the preservice teachers in the current research negotiated and renegotiated their teaching philosophy in part due to the influence of their experiences with members of their school community.

For example, while Ruthie described that developing a teaching philosophy required time and experience, she identified an awareness of what she wanted to give her students as a teacher:- [my philosophy of teaching] is more along the lines of equitable opportunities for all kids. So, that's what I'm there for, to provide those opportunities and make sure that all children are treated equitably...It [school] should be enjoyable and a safe place for them to be (Ruthie, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Self-confidence can play a part in the formation of a teaching philosophy, as it was the case for Jacinda: Through the immersion pathway, I have thoroughly developed that skill...my teacher identity is well developed at this point in time and I think as I continue to teach it will continue to develop...I see myself as a teacher now (Jacinda, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Yet, a preservice teacher's sense of confidence can be fragile and vulnerable to change when confronted with new challenges. Jacinda shared an example of a point in time during her professional experience at her school when she questioned her professional competency:

My class was more difficult and I was not receiving the mentoring that I had experienced in the [volunteer days of the] immersion pathway. So, I was actually thinking, 'Am I actually worthwhile as a teacher? Is this really where I need to be?' ...But that lasted about a week and then I managed to get that under control and that reinforced the teaching thing again (Jacinda, Interview 3, November, 2015).

For Jacinda, a lack of support from her second supervising teacher during her professional experience appeared to constrain her ability to become prepared for subsequent involvement in related teaching practices (in the second half of the year) that she perceived herself to be able to manage in the first half of the year during her engagement in the immersion pathway. This finding appears to be in contrast with those found about preservice teachers in a study by Caires et al. (2012) which described

preservice teachers' growing levels of autonomy, self-confidence, and trust about the quality of the skills and knowledge that they acquired during teaching practice. Jacinda's account of her fluctuating self-belief and teacher identity and the change of teaching environment illustrated the ongoing process of teacher identity development.

Written reflections, such as journals or note-taking represented professional artefacts which assisted preservice teachers in expressing their thoughts and experiences about teaching and learning (Wray, 2007) and their educational philosophies. Continual reflection on university coursework helped Kaeley to reconsider how she wanted to relate to her students. Kaeley, as part of her university coursework, and as was the case for all of the preservice teachers, had to complete 20 hours of voluntary Service learning in the local community. She selected to work with students and staff in the Students with Disabilities (SWD) Centre at her school. This experience made her reconsider her teaching approach which had a significant influence on her developing teaching philosophy:

...[I would write] a few notes down every day after I'd finished just helped clear my mind about what I had been doing. I did it [Service learning] in the SWD Centre. It really opened my eyes up to the individual differences of all these students, the parents, and the community...I've never experienced these forms of poverty...It has really affected me so much so I think that the way that I'm teaching is changing...That it's a bit more student relationship-focused rather than just worrying about student results (Kaeley, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Kaeley's comments reflect a common situation described in contemporary research, that is to say, a majority of primary school teachers in Australia are middle-class females with Anglo-Australian backgrounds, and they have had little exposure to children with backgrounds as diverse as what they witness during school-based professional experience (Connelly & Joske, 2001; Hodgetts, 2010).

Raquel's engagement in a disadvantaged school gave her a strong sense of responsibility toward her students' well-being and seemed to make her want to offer her students some things that their home life might be deficient in giving them:

Their achievements and accomplishments should be celebrated...I think that by having a classroom that provides that and encourages that then you're more likely to have children that will try that little bit extra harder maybe because they know that they're valued and that you want them to be there, whereas at home they might not get that (Raquel, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Preservice teachers tend to enter teacher education with an idealised image of teaching with little knowledge of the everyday realities of a teacher's life (Correa, Martínez-Arbeláiz, & Gutierrez, 2014). Yet, while the preservice teachers involved in the

immersion pathway all had prior short-term placements in schools of various socio-economic status, Ruthie, Jacinda, and Kaeley shared insights they gained by being immersed in a disadvantaged school environment for an extended period of time and they shared how this exposure influenced the way they perceived their teaching philosophy.

In addition to reflecting on their current roles as teachers in the immersion pathway, the preservice teachers reflected on what their future teaching selves would be.

6.2 Future Teaching

Without explicit guidance when writing a statement of teaching philosophy, preservice teachers may struggle with expressing how their pedagogical philosophies are related to their epistemological beliefs or their perceived future effectiveness as teachers (Moseti Ongaki, 2014). Yet, in the current study, the preservice teachers were able to explain their developing philosophy of teaching orally and connect their beliefs to their future as teaching professionals.

For Elizabeth, her engagement in a disadvantaged school gave her a sense of understanding about the best school setting for her future teaching career:

I still want to make a difference but I want to do it in these schools with these kids because that's where it's needed. I suppose that's part of my professional identity, wanting to make a difference in those particular schools (Elizabeth, Interview 3, November, 2015).

In her immediate future, Susanna felt that cultivating relationships with her students and focusing on the setup of her classroom were important elements of her developing teaching practice for when she teaches in her own classroom next year as a beginning teacher:

...building that rapport and relationship with your children is going to be like my Number One initial thing with setting up my room and meeting a new class and that kind of thing because I think that it sets the expectation but it sets you up for the rest of the year. Your life is so much easier when you have a class that respects you and you respect them (Susanna, Interview 1, March, 2015).

The degree to which preservice teachers in the current study perceived their supervising teachers as meeting their 'idealised' standards influenced how they saw their future selves as teachers (Furlong, 2013) and their developing philosophy of teaching. Susanna appeared to feel that she owed much of her student-oriented teaching philosophy to the relationships she observed in the classroom between her supervising teachers and students. These relationship dynamics affected her developing professional identity, her thinking about teaching, and how she wants to be seen by her students in the future:

She's [her supervising teacher]...shown me the kind of teacher that I would like to be. I'm basing a lot of my beliefs and values as a teacher on how she runs her classroom because I've never seen a class that adores their teacher as much as these guys already adore her (Susanna, Interview 1, March, 2015).

A philosophy of teaching that considered aspects of both one's current and future teaching affords preservice teachers with greater clarity of their professional identity and competency in their teaching practices.

VII. DISCUSSION

Awareness of their developing philosophy of teaching was significant for the participants in this research as they were required to write an essay on this topic for their teacher registration application (Queensland College of Teachers, n.d.). So, this concept appeared to often be at the forefront of the preservice teachers' thinking, particularly toward the end of their stay in the school community. Their philosophy of teaching seemed to be strongly connected to their perception of self-as-teachers.

As discussed in the literature review, the notion that preservice teachers can benefit from engaging in a process of self-reflection about their growing professional identities based on their observations and experiences appeared to be the case for participants in the current study. Self-reflection can provide a lens through which the individual can develop an understanding of who he/she is within his/her multiple roles and how others see him/her (Danielwicz, 2001). Several preservice teachers indicated that had developed an awareness of a need to be flexible in their approach to interacting with members of their school community. Furthermore, some preservice teachers shared how their experience of interacting with students at disadvantaged schools had a significant effect on their teaching philosophy and self-image of their future professional selves. The researcher found that there is little available research about the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching in an immersion pathway. So, this is an area worth exploring more so that teacher educators can better understand how best to support teacher identity development.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

Two limitations to the current research should be considered. Firstly, the sample of participants was limited to six individuals. So, only general conclusions can be made from the findings presented. The findings cannot be viewed as being general representations of the experiences of Australia-based preservice teachers. Secondly, preservice teachers' self-reporting behaviours had the potential to present opportunities for inaccuracies and/or bias to occur during data collection. So, the researcher allowed the

participants freedom in writing content via the online discussion board either publicly within the group or privately with the researcher, and this served to minimise the risk of potential bias and/or inaccuracies in the preservice teachers' self-reporting.

CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

In relation to the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching, data in the current study revealed preservice teacher appreciation and enthusiasm for in working in disadvantaged schools in their future, as well as their interest in meeting their students' needs in the classroom and in helping those students to become aware of the value of education in their future lives. While there is little research to be found on the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching in an immersion pathway, this is an area worth exploring more so that a greater understanding of how best to support preservice teacher identity development can be constructed.

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TABLES

Type of participation & number of participants	Total number of participants	Time
Interview (1 st round: early in the year) 2 individual & 1 unplanned group of 4	6	4 th week of March & 1 st week of April
Interview (2 nd round: mid-year) 4 individual & 1 unplanned group of 2	6	1 st week of July
Interview (3 rd round: end of the year) 3 individual & 1 unplanned group of 3	6	1 st & 2 nd week of November
Online discussion board (5 out of 6)	5	From 1 st week of March to 4 th week of October

Table 1.1 - Schedule for Participants in Online Discussion Board & Interviews

Participant	School	Year level(s)	Age	Number of children	Age of children
Elizabeth	A	4, 5, 6	21	0	N/A
Jacinda	B	5, 6	21	0	N/A
Susanna	C	4	23	0	N/A
Kaeley	D	3, 4	45	2	10 & 6
Raquel	E	1, 3	40	2	14 & 2
Ruthie	E & C	1, 3/4	41	2	14 & 11

Table 1.2 - Information of Participants